

ISOLATION OF NATURAL DYE FROM CODIAEUM VARIEGATUM

Khalida Tasneem^{*} , Rajiv Khatioda

Department of Chemistry,
North Eastern Regional Institute of Science and Technology
(Deemed University), Itanagar , India

Abstract

The powdered dried leaves of Codiaeum Variegatum “ garden croton” or Variegated croton” refluxed with alcohol for 12 hours. Natural dye obtained was then applied on wool using different mordants gave beautiful parrot green, light green, light brown and dark brown shades.

Codiaeum Variegatum is a species of plant in the genus Codiaeum, which is a member Of the family Euphorbiaceae. It is native to southern India, Sri Lanka, Indonesia, Malaysia and the Western Pacific Ocean islands, growing in open forests and scrub. It is an evergreen shrub growing to 3m tall and has large, thick, leathery , shiny evergreen leaves, alternately arranged, 30 cm long and 0.5-8 cm broad.

Preparation of Natural Dye and its application on wool with different mordants :-

The macerated leaves of Codiaeum Variegatum was refluxed with alcohol for 12 hours ,filtered and the solvent was evaporated in rotator apparatus under reduced pressure, the solid residue obtained as natural dye was treated with wool with 10% and 20% of mordants copper sulphate, Ferrous sulphate and potassium dichromate. Boiling wool with natural dye and mordant for one hour. Washing of dyed wool with water and than drying in shade at room temperature. In all cases same timing and same procedure was applied. Mordanting helps the dye bind to the fibre. Different mordants allow different colour ranges for each dyestuff.

The amount of mordant used was a percentage of the weight of fibre.It was important to note the different in shades when the wool was first mordanting then dyeing, than the colour of wool first dyeing then mordanting.Also the shades changes with the increase in the percentage of modants taking the percentage of dye same. There was also change in shades when first dyeing and than mordanting.

Key words: Codiaeum Variegatum, dye,

OBSERVATION AND SHADE CARD

5.1 Observations:

Preparation of mordants				
Mordants	10% of 200mg wool	20% of 200mg wool	Amount of water (ml)	Observation
Copper sulphate	20mg	40mg	100	Blue
Ferrous sulphate	20mg	40mg	100	Yellow
Potassium dichromate	20mg	40mg	100	Orange

Mordants with dye						
Dye	20mg copper sulphate	40mg copper sulphate	20mg ferrous sulphate	40mg ferrous sulphate	20mg potassium dichromate	40mg potassium dichromate
20 mg Codiaeum Variegatum	Light yellow colour	Parrot green colour	Muddy colour	Muddy colour	Yellow colour	Yellow colour

Colour of wool 1st mordanting then dyeing :

Sl. No	Sample	Composition (Mordant + Dye)
1		10% Copper Sulphate + 10% dye
2		20% Copper Sulphate + 10% dye
3		10% Ferrous Sulphate + 10% dye
4		20% Ferrous Sulphate + 10% dye
5		10% Potassium dichromate + 10% dye
6		20% Potassium dichromate + 10% dye

Colour of wool 1st Dyeing then mordanting :

Sl. No	Sample	Composition (Dye+ Mordant)
1		10% dye + 10% Copper Sulphate
2		10% dye + 20% Copper Sulphate
3		10% dye + 10% Ferrous Sulphate
4		10% dye + 20% Ferrous Sulphate
5		10% dye + 10% Potassium dichromate
6		10% dye + 20% Potassium dichromate

CONCLUSION :-

The dye- bath colour was not representative of the ending wool colour. With the higher concentration of mordant the wool seemed to absorb the dye better , thus dyeing darker. The variation of mordants created a variety of different effects in wool colour wise. The mordants didn't effect the texture of the wool. Mordants have been proved to be useful chemicals in the natural dyeing process.

BIBLIOGRAPHY:-

BIBLIOGRAPHY:

1. Perkin, A. G. and Everest, A. E., The natural Organic Colouring Matters, Longmans, Green and co., London.(1948).
2. The wealth of India, Raw Material, Vol. 3 A-B, CSIR, 9 (1948)
3. Scholt, Elizabeth in "Dye plants and Dying" a handbook(plants and Garden),Brooklyn Botanic Garden Record, Brooklyn Botanic Garden, Brooklyn, New York, Vol. 20(3), 38 (1964).
4. Edelstien, Sidney M., in dye plants and Dyeing a handbook(Plants and Garden),Brooklyn Botanic Garden Records, Brooklyn Botanic Garden, Brooklyn, New York, Vol. 20(3),9 (1969).
5. Thrustan, V., The use of vegetable Dyes, Dryad Press, Leicester, England (1967).
5. Duncan, M., "Spin your own wool and dye it and weave it" A.H. and A.W. Reed, Wellington, New Zealand (1968).
6. Colour index, Vol.4, 5, 6, 3rd edition , Society of dryers Colourist (SDC), Perkin House, Bradford, U.K. (1971).
7. Wickens, H.M., "Natural Dyes for Spinners and Weavers", London (1983).
8. "Indian Natural Colouring Agents" beyond 2000 AD held at Lucknow, Feb. 2000.
9. Convention of Natural Dyes, Dec. 2001 at IIT Delhi.
10. Krishna G. Bhattacharya and Arunima Sharma, Dyes pigment, Vol. 57(3), 2003, 211-222.
11. T. Bechtold, A. Turcanu, E. Ganglberg, Journal of Cleaner Production, Vol. 2(5), 2003, 499 509.
12. Tae-Kying Kilm, Seok-Han, Dyes Pigments, Vol. 60(2), 2004, 121-127.
13. Sorapong Janhom, Peter Griffiths, Sorosak Watanesk, Dyes Pigments, Vol. 63(3), 2004, 231-237.
14. M.M. Kamal, Reda m., Dyes Pigments, Vol. 65(2), 2005, 103-110.
15. Rajni Singh, Astha Jain, Shikh, Dyes and Pigments, Vol. 66(2), Aug. 2005, 99-102.
16. A. K. Prusty, A. Nayak , A. Purohit and N.B. Das, Colourage, January 2010, 55-56.
17. Pier Luigi Beltrame, Anadrea Mossa, Giovanni Testa, Dyes Pigments, Vol. 39 (4), 1998, 335-340.